

color key

Bio-based materials

	Wood	CLT slab CLT wall glulam MDF OSB parquet structural timber wood battens
	Bio-based insulation	straw insulation wood fiber insulation wood fibre board wood wool insulation cellulose insulation cork cotton insulation flax fiber insulation
	Other bio-based materials	rammed earth substrate

Fossil-based materials

	Plastics	PE foil PU coating roofing membrane rubber granulate mat synthetic material bitumen membrane bitumen primer drainage
	Fossil-based insulation	PIR insulation XPS insulation cement-bound EPS fill EPS facade EPS impact sound insulation EPS roof
	Other fossil energy materials	polymer-modified mortar pre-coat synthetic resin plaster asphalt

Metal materials

	Aluminum	aluminium
	Steel	steel steel plate steel reinforcement

Non-metallic minerals

	Brick	perforated brick sand-lime brick solid brick roof tiles
	Concrete	aerated concrete concrete concrete block concrete deep foundation concrete recycling concrete slab concrete wall screed
	Glass	glass
	Mineral insulation	perlite fill foamed glass gravel glass wool insulation mineral wool facade mineral wool impact sound insulation mineral wool interior mineral wool pitched roof mineral wool roof
	Other non-metallic minerals	linoleum plasterboard tiles cement plaster clay plaster fiber cement roof panels fiber-reinforced concrete fire-rated plasterboard gravel gravel fill gypsum fiber panel gypsum plaster lightweight expanded clay fill lime-cement plaster

Undefined materials

	Undefined materials	venetian blinds window roof windows plastic windows wood windows wood/aluminum door
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EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: TRIO.inklusiv
Architects: einszueins architektur

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	314
storage	-8
306 kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	372
storage	-9
363 kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	

General:

Country	Austria
Region	Vienna
Finished	2025
Typology	Multi-family house
Structure	massive concrete

Area:

GFA total(ag+bg)	21 391 m²
above ground	17 210 m²
below ground	4 181 m²
NFA total(ag+bg)	18 291 m²
above ground	14 495 m²
below ground	3 796 m²
Ratio NFA/GFA	86 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):

Individual	67 %
Shared	11 %
community	2 %
infrastructure	9 %
Commercial	0 %
Other	22 %

Usage:

Number of users	392
Average unit size	68 m²
Average individual area	31 m²
Average enjoyable area	320 m²
GWP (A1-A3)/person	13 417 kgCO₂e/ppl.

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: OASE.inklusiv
Architects: einszueins architektur

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	283
storage	-16
267 kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	348
storage	-19
329 kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	

General:

Country	Austria
Region	Vienna
Finished	2021
Typology	Multi-family house
Structure	massive concrete

Area:

GFA total(ag+bg)	11 222 m²
above ground	8 785 m²
below ground	2 437 m²
NFA total(ag+bg)	9 412 m²
above ground	7 134 m²
below ground	2 278 m²
Ratio NFA/GFA	84 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):

Individual	63 %
Shared	12 %
community	5 %
infrastructure	7 %
Commercial	0 %
Other	25 %

Usage:

Number of users	177
Average unit size	73 m²
Average individual area	33 m²
Average enjoyable area	478 m²
GWP (A1-A3)/person	13 245 kgCO₂e/ppl.

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Wohnprojekt Gleis 21
Architects: einzueins architektur

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	270
storage	-99
171 kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	310
storage	-114
196 kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	

General:	
Country	Austria
Region	Vienna
Finished	2019
Typology	Mixed use
Structure	frame wood

Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	5 451 m²
above ground	4 507 m²
below ground	944 m²
NFA total(ag+bg)	4 701 m²
above ground	3 924 m²
below ground	777 m²
Ratio NFA/GFA	86 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	55 %
Shared	27 %
community	8 %
infrastructure	19 %
Commercial	11 %
Other	8 %

Usage:	
Number of users	77
Average unit size	76 m²
Average individual area	33 m²
Average enjoyable area	428 m²

Module	kgCO ₂ e	kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag
A1-A3	769 791	170,8	196,2
A4,A5	23 109	5,1	5,9
B4	0	0,0	0,0
B6	0	0,0	0,0
C1,C2	40 671	9,0	10,4
C3,C4	549 243	121,9	140,0
D	0	0,0	0,0
Total	1 382 814	306,8	352,4

Assessment methodology:	
RSP	50 years
Database	Ökobaudat
Software	SCALE, Madaster, Archicad
Building systems	Surcharge 30 kgCO ₂ -Äq/GFA
*Due to a lack of data, modules A4+A5, B4 and C1+C2 cannot yet be fully accounted for.	
Assumption: The electricity mix is carbon-neutral by 2050: No	

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: KooWo
Architects: Schwarz-Platzer Architekten

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	208
storage	-323
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	261
storage	-405

General:	
Country	Austria
Region	Volkersdorf, Styria
Finished	2019
Typology	Row house
Structure	frame wood

Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	4 083 m ²
above ground	3 665 m ²
below ground	418 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	3 266 m ²
above ground	2 922 m ²
below ground	344 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	80 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	67 %
Shared	18 %
community	16 %
infrastructure	2 %
Commercial	3 %
Other	12 %

Usage:	
Number of users	71
Average unit size	553 m ²
Average individual area	31 m ²
Average enjoyable area	78 m ²
GWP (A1-A3)/person	-5 925 kgCO ₂ e/ppl.

Module	kgCO ₂ e	kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag
A1-A3	-420 703	-114,8	-144,0
A4,A5	20 690	5,6	7,1
B4	0	0,0	0,0
B6	0	0,0	0,0
C1,C2	17 643	4,8	6,0
C3,C4	1 236 209	337,3	423,1
D	0	0,0	0,0
Total	853 839	233,0	292,2

Assessment methodology:	
RSP	50 years
Database	Ökobaudat
Software	SCALE, Madaster, Archicad
Building systems	Surcharge 30 kgCO ₂ -Äq/GFA
*Due to a lack of data, modules A4+A5, B4 and C1+C2 cannot yet be fully accounted for.	
Assumption: The electricity mix is carbon-neutral by 2050: No	

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Cirerers
Architects: Celobert cooperativa

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	236
storage	-299
kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
-63	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	274
storage	-349
kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	
-74	

General:

Country	Spain
Region	Barcelona
Finished	2022
Typology	Multi-family house
Structure	massive wood

Area:

GFA total(ag+bg)	2 467 m ²
above ground	2 467 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	2 118 m ²
above ground	2 118 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	86 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):

Individual	72 %
Shared	19 %
community	4 %
infrastructure	15 %
Commercial	5 %
Other	4 %

Usage:

Number of users	62
Average unit size	48 m ²
Average individual area	25 m ²
Average enjoyable area	107 m ²
GWP (A1-A3)/person	-2 520 kgCO ₂ e/ppl.

Assessment methodology:

RSP	50 years
Database	Ökobaudat
Software	SCALE, Madaster, Archicad
Building systems	Surcharge 30 kgCO ₂ -Äq/GFA

*Due to a lack of data, modules A4+A5, B4 and C1+C2 cannot yet be fully accounted for.

Assumption: The electricity mix is carbon-neutral by 2050: No

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: La Chalmeta
Architects: Pau Vidal + Vivas Arquitectos

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	347
storage	-21
326 kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	409
storage	-25
384 kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	

General:	
Country	Spain
Region	Barcelona
Finished	2021
Typology	Multi-family house
Structure	massive concrete

Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	3 417 m ²
above ground	3 417 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	2 902 m ²
above ground	2 902 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	85 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	72 %
Shared	17 %
community	3 %
infrastructure	15 %
Commercial	8 %
Other	3 %

Usage:	
Number of users	65
Average unit size	65 m ²
Average individual area	32 m ²
Average enjoyable area	107 m ²
GWP (A1-A3)/person	17 157 kgCO ₂ e/ppl.

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Les P'tits Ensemble(s)
Architects: Atelier Belenfant Daubas

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	211
storage	-247
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	256
storage	-299

General:	
Country	France
Region	Guérande
Finished	2018
Typology	Multi-family house
Structure	frame wood

Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	1019 m ²
above ground	1019 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	841 m ²
above ground	841 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	83 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	77 %
Shared	12 %
community	7 %
infrastructure	5 %
Commercial	0 %
Other	12 %

Usage:	
Number of users	25
Average unit size	65 m ²
Average individual area	26 m ²
Average enjoyable area	81 m ²

Module	kgCO ₂ e	kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag
A1-A3	-36 440	-35,8	-43,3
A4,A5	3 134	3,1	3,7
B4	0	0,0	0,0
B6	0	0,0	0,0
C1,C2	3 485	3,4	4,1
C3,C4	267 766	262,8	318,4
D	0	0,0	0,0
Total	237 944	233,5	282,9

Assessment methodology:

RSP	50 years
Database	Ökobaudat
Software	SCALE, Madaster, Archicad
Building systems	Surcharge 30 kgCO ₂ -Äq/GFA

*Due to a lack of data, modules A4+A5, B4 and C1+C2 cannot yet be fully accounted for.

Assumption: The electricity mix is carbon-neutral by 2050: No

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Coteau de La Chaudanne
Architects: Armand Barthélémy

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	202
storage	-226
kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	254
storage	-284
kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	

General:	
Country	France
Region	Rhone -Alpes
Finished	2016
Typology	Row house
Structure	frame wood

Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	2 284 m ²
above ground	2 200 m ²
below ground	84 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	1 824 m ²
above ground	1 754 m ²
below ground	70 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	80 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	88 %
Shared	9 %
community	9 %
infrastructure	0 %
Commercial	0 %
Other	3 %

Usage:	
Number of users	35
Average unit size	107 m ²
Average individual area	46 m ²
Average enjoyable area	214 m ²

Module	kgCO ₂ e	kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag
A1-A3	-52 829	-24,0	-30,1
A4,A5	6 750	3,1	3,8
B4	0	0,0	0,0
B6	0	0,0	0,0
C1,C2	10 325	4,7	5,9
C3,C4	536 479	243,9	305,9
D	0	0,0	0,0
Total	500 725	227,6	285,5

Assessment methodology:	
RSP	50 years
Database	Ökobaudat
Software	SCALE, Madaster, Archicad
Building systems	Surcharge 30 kgCO ₂ -Äq/GFA
*Due to a lack of data, modules A4+A5, B4 and C1+C2 cannot yet be fully accounted for.	
Assumption: The electricity mix is carbon-neutral by 2050: No	

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Iewan
Architects: Orio architecten

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	190
storage	-136
54 kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	233
storage	-167
67 kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	

General:	
Country	Netherlands
Region	Nijmegen
Finished	2015
Typology	Mixed use
Structure	frame wood
Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	2 865 m ²
above ground	2 865 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	2 330 m ²
above ground	2 330 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	81 %
Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	69 %
Shared	25 %
community	15 %
infrastructure	10 %
Commercial	0 %
Other	6 %
Usage:	
Number of users	54
Average unit size	67 m ²
Average individual area	30 m ²
Average enjoyable area	379 m ²
GWP (A1-A3)/person	2 874 kgCO ₂ e/ppl.

Module	kgCO ₂ e	kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag
A1-A3	155 194	54,2	66,6
A4,A5	9 666	3,4	4,1
B4	0	0,0	0,0
B6	0	0,0	0,0
C1,C2	10 628	3,7	4,6
C3,C4	444 368	155,1	190,7
D	0	0,0	0,0
Total	619 855	216,4	266,0

Assessment methodology:

RSP	50 years
Database	Ökobaudat
Software	SCALE, Madaster, Archicad
Building systems	Surcharge 30 kgCO ₂ -Äq/GFA

*Due to a lack of data, modules A4+A5, B4 and C1+C2 cannot yet be fully accounted for.

Assumption: The electricity mix is carbon-neutral by 2050: No

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Torteltuim
Architects: Natrufried

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	326
storage	-287
39 kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	385
storage	-339
46 kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	

General:	
Country	Netherlands
Region	Amsterdam
Finished	2026
Typology	Mixed use
Structure	massive wood
Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	4 181 m ²
above ground	3 146 m ²
below ground	1 035 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	3 569 m ²
above ground	2 667 m ²
below ground	902 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	85 %
Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	53 %
Shared	22 %
community	12 %
infrastructure	10 %
Commercial	0 %
Other	26 %
Usage:	
Number of users	65
Average unit size	47 m ²
Average individual area	29 m ²
Average enjoyable area	447 m ²
GWP (A1-A3)/person	1 898 kgCO ₂ e/ppl.

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Hobelwerk , Haus D
Architects: Pascal Flammer Architekten

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	236
storage	-324
kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
-88	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	277
storage	-381
kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	
-103	

General:	
Country	Switzerland
Region	Winterthur/Zurich
Finished	2023
Typology	Mixed use
Structure	frame wood

Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	2 500 m ²
above ground	2 500 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	2 128 m ²
above ground	2 128 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	85 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	42 %
Shared	46 %
community	31 %
infrastructure	15 %
Commercial	9 %
Other	4 %

Usage:	
Number of users	63
Average unit size	64 m ²
Average individual area	14 m ²
Average enjoyable area	673 m ²

Module	kgCO ₂ e	kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag
A1-A3	-219 151	-87,7	-103,0
A4,A5	14 396	5,8	6,8
B4	0	0,0	0,0
B6	0	0,0	0,0
C1,C2	9 935	4,0	4,7
C3,C4	833 721	333,5	391,8
D	0	0,0	0,0
Total	638 902	255,6	300,2

Assessment methodology:	
RSP	50 years
Database	Ökobaudat
Software	SCALE, Madaster, Archicad
Building systems	Surcharge 30 kgCO ₂ -Äq/GFA
*Due to a lack of data, modules A4+A5, B4 and C1+C2 cannot yet be fully accounted for.	
Assumption: The electricity mix is carbon-neutral by 2050: No	

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Miteinander im Wiesental
 Architects: office03

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	233
storage	-173
60 kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	284
storage	-211
73 kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	

General:	
Country	Germany
Region	Aachen
Finished	2023
Typology	Multi-family house
Structure	frame wood

Area:	
GFA total(ag+bg)	1983 m ²
above ground	1983 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
NFA total(ag+bg)	1628 m ²
above ground	1628 m ²
below ground	0 m ²
Ratio NFA/GFA	82 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):	
Individual	78 %
Shared	16 %
community	4 %
infrastructure	12 %
Commercial	0 %
Other	6 %

Usage:	
Number of users	35
Average unit size	85 m ²
Average individual area	36 m ²
Average enjoyable area	102 m ²
GWP (A1-A3)/person	3 382 kgCO ₂ e/ppl.

